

International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes

EB-ICSP Meeting 28th May 2026 – Redacted Minutes

Chair:
E.R.B. MOORE
University of Gothenburg
Sweden

Vice-Chair:
C.M. MANAIA
Universidade Católica Portuguesa
Portugal

Executive Secretary:
A. OREN
Hebrew University of Jerusalem
Israel

Secretary for Subcommittees:
S.L.W. ON
Lincoln University
New Zealand

Treasurer:
P. NIELSEN
Novozymes, Copenhagen
Denmark

Members at Large:
R. HAHNKE
Leibniz Institute DSMZ
Germany

M. SAKAMOTO
RIKEN BioResource
Research Center
Japan

**Members of the Judicial
Committee**

Chair:
D.R. ARAHAL
University of Valencia
Spain

Vice-Chair:
H. CHRISTENSEN
University of Copenhagen
Denmark

Secretary:
M. GÖKER
Leibniz Institute DSMZ
Germany

Minute 1. The Chair called the meeting to order at 10.00 CEST.

Minute 2. Record of attendance

The following members of the Executive Board (EB) participated: E.R.B. Moore (Chair), C.M. Manaia (Vice-Chair), A. Oren (Executive Secretary), S.L.W. On (Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy), R. Hahnke (Member-at-Large), M. Sakamoto (Member-at-Large), M. del C. Montero-Calasanz (Vice-Chair JC), and M. Göker (Secretary JC). Apologies were received from P. Nielsen (Treasurer) and D.R. Arahal (Chair JC).

Minute 3. Minutes of the 30th April 2026 meeting of the EB

The draft minutes of the 30th April meeting were approved. A. Oren will circulate the minutes to the members of the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes (ICSP), the Judicial Commission (JC), and chairs of the Subcommittees on Taxonomy, and he will send a copy to E.R.B. Moore to be posted on the ICSP website.

Minute 4. Matters Arising/Action points from previous meetings

A. Oren has forwarded the redacted minutes of the 26th March meeting of the EB to all members of the ICSP, the Judicial Commission and the chairs of the Subcommittees on Taxonomy.

E.R.B. Moore has posted the redacted minutes of the 26th March meeting of the EB on the ICSP website.

M. Göker has prepared and circulated a Word version of the text of the 2025 revision of the ICNP, including the most recent corrections.

A. Oren sent reminders to the ICSP members who had not returned the ballot for appointment of eight co-opted members.

A. Oren sent reminders to the ICSP members who had not returned the ballot for endorsement of JC opinions 133 and 134.

E.R.B. Moore and R. Hahnke sent reminders to the ICSP members who had not returned the ballot for appointment of M.-S. Li to replace A. Ventosa as a member of the JC.

C.M. Manaia has finalized the draft table outlining the ways different types of submissions such as ICSP reports and meeting minutes must be handled by the *IJSEM* editors and the production staff. See Minute 13.

International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes

S.L.W. On has contacted the officers of the ICSP Subcommittees on the Taxonomy of *Borrelia* and *Neisseria* to obtain relevant information to be posted on the ICSP website. See Minute 15.

E.R.B. Moore and M. Göker have contacted NCBI about the NCBI-hosted “Unifying Prokaryotic Taxonomy” microsession during the ASM-2026 Microbe conference to clarify that the ICNP mandate and activities deals with all prokaryotes, cultivated and uncultivated.

A. Oren did not yet to prepare the ballot for election of EB officers as the ballot formate was not yet defined by the EB. See Minute 6.

E.R.B. Moore has forwarded nomination letters for the election of Life Members to A. Oren. See Minute 8.

A. Oren did not yet send out the ballot for the election of Life Members. See Minute 8.

E.R.B. Moore has contacted the EB members who did not attend the 30th April meeting and asked for their opinion on the proposal submitted by M. del C. Montero Calasanz and M. Göker to convert the Working Group on Education and Outreach to an Ad Hoc Subcommittee, in accordance with the ICSP statutes. Two voting members were in favor, five were against.

E.R.B. Moore has contacted the University of Queensland to confirm the status of the nomination of an awardee of the van Niel International Prize. See Minute 9.

A. Oren has notified T.W.F. Aaron that the EB has accepted the invitation from BISMis to present a summary of the milestones and key achievements of the ICSP and the outgoing term of the EB in a BISMis Live session. See Minute 10.

A. Oren and E.R.B. Moore have welcomed M. del C. Montero Calasanz, the new Vice-Chair of the JC, to the EB.

Minute 5. Update Full-members appointed for the new term

A. Oren reported that no new full members were appointed by IUMS-affiliated societies since the previous EB meeting.

Minute 6. Update on Officer positions for the EB-ICSP in the new term

E.R.B. Moore and A. Oren reported that the following candidate statements were received: for Chair: E.R.B. Moore; for Vice-Chair, M. Šeruga Musić; for Executive Secretary: M. Kostovski; for Secretary for Subcommittees: H. Christensen; for Treasurer: T.W.F. Aaron. For the two Member-at-Large positions there are five candidates: I. Kurtböke, J.-S. Lee, M. Sakamoto, A. Sidarenko, and J.A. Vázquez-Boland. A. Oren will prepare the ballot and anticipates to start the voting on 1st June. A. Oren and C.M. Manaia will serve as the tellers.

Minute 7. Update on Co-opted-members

A. Oren reported that 48 (72%) of the 67 full members returned the ballot for election of Co-opted members. A. Oren and C.M. Manaia served as the tellers. All candidates were supported with large majorities: T.W.F. Aaron; Y. Kawamura; R.R. de la Haba; I. Kurtböke; J. Martin-Rodriguez; A. Nemic; A. Sidarenka; J. Tambong; A. Thamchaipenet.

International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes

Minute 8. Update on nominations and elections for Life Members

E.R.B. Moore and A. Oren reported that nomination letters have been received to propose life memberships to H.-J. Busse, L. Dijkshoorn, and E. Stackebrandt. A. Oren will prepare the ballot. The voting is anticipated to start on 1st June. A. Oren and P. Nielsen will serve as the tellers.

Minute 9. Update on the IUMS Conference, Lisbon, November 2026

The University of Queensland has confirmed the ICSP nomination and awarded the C.B. van Niel International Prize for Studies in Bacterial Systematics for the term of 2023-2026 to J. Chung (Seoul National University and CJ Bioscience, Republic of Korea). J. Chung has agreed to accept the prize and give the prize lecture at the ICSP Session of the IUMS 2026 Biennial Congress in Lisbon, Portugal in November. The EB unanimously agreed to financially support Dr. Chung's travel with Euro 2,000 and the conference registration fee, if applicable, to be financed from the Skerman funds of the ICSP bank account. E.R.B. Moore and A. Oren will publish the decision to award the prize to J. Chun in the *IJSEM*. The awarding ceremony and prize lecture, scheduled to last 35 min, will be followed by a 25 min talk informing the audience about the mandate and activities of the ICSP, to be presented by E.R.B. Moore, M. Göker or R. Hahnke. E.R.B. Moore will notify the organizers of the IUMS conference of the program of the 1-hr ICSP sponsored session. This session will be followed by a 1.5-hr workshop on microbial taxonomy, moderated by A. Yurkov.

Minute 10. Invite by T.W.F. Aaron to a BISMis Live session to present ICSP

A. Oren has notified T.W.F. Aaron that the ICSP EB has accepted the invitation to present a BISMis Live session, and that Saturday 18th July is the most suitable date, as E.R.B. Moore, A. Oren, M. Göker and M. del C. Montero-Calasanz will be available to present, and C.M. Manaia, P. Nielsen, and M. Sakamoto will be able to attend online. A. Oren will coordinate the format and content of the 45-min presentation with E.R.B. Moore, A. Oren, M. Göker and M. del C. Montero-Calasanz.

Minute 11. Update from the JC

M.-S. Li has been elected with a large majority to the JC to replace A. Ventosa. Of the 69 members eligible to vote (full and life members), 52 (75%) had returned the ballot; E.R.B. Moore and R. Hahnke served as the tellers. The JC unanimously appointed M. del C. Montero-Calasanz as its Vice-Chair. M. Göker and M. del C. Montero-Calasanz have found a number of candidates for the 26th class of commissioners. The ballot to elect the new commissioners should start no later than 15th July.

The voting members of the ICSP have endorsed Opinion 133 (45 in favor, 0 against, 1 abstention) and Opinion 134 (42 in favor, 0 against, 4 abstentions).

Minute 12. Update from the Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP

A. Oren has received a Word version of the text of the 2025 revision of the ICNP from M. Göker. There were no further updates.

International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes

Minute 13. Update from *IJSEM* and Publications Committee

Work on the draft that C.M. Manaia has prepared, outlining the ways different types of submissions such as ICSP reports and meeting minutes must be handled by the *IJSEM* editors and the production staff, is ongoing. There were no further updates.

Minute 14. Update from the Treasurer

The bank account of the ICSP is currently closed due to lack of business review. P. Nielsen is currently trying to solve the problem.

Minute 15. Update from Subcommittees on Taxonomy

S.L.W. On has collected information about the officers of the respective ICSP Subcommittees on the Taxonomy of *Borrelia* and *Neisseria* to be posted on the ICSP website. G. Margos is the chair of the subcommittee on *Borrelia*. F. Veyrier and E. Bille are chair and secretary of the *Neisseria* subcommittee, respectively. M. Göker added that Brian Stevenson is the secretary of the *Borrelia* subcommittee.

Minute 16. Update from Working Groups and Ad Hoc Committees

After the EB had discussed the proposal submitted by M. del C. Montero Calasanz and M. Göker to convert the Working Group on Education and Outreach to an Ad Hoc Subcommittee, in accordance with the ICSP statutes at the 30th April meeting, two EB members supported the proposal, and five voted against. E.R.B. Moore invited the members that voted against the proposal to explain their reasons. M. del C. Montero-Calasanz requested to know why the majority of members objected. Although, EB members are not obligated to explain their voting, EB members who agree to share such information may contact S.L.W. On no later than 26th June, and he will then summarize the comments received and forward them anonymously to M. del C. Montero-Calasanz and M. Göker.

The working group on availability of type strains had nothing to report.

Minute 17. Status of promotion of the ICSP on LinkedIn

M. Göker reported that the ICSP currently has 432 followers on LinkedIn. He did not yet finish his inquiry on what advantages upgrading the account to LinkedIn Premium may have.

E.R.B. Moore reported that the ICSP website was recently updated and further updates will follow, with the changes of the start of the new term

Minute 18. Any other business

A. Oren mentioned that J.A. Vázquez-Boland and 10 co-authors associated with the ICSP, its EB or the JC, had submitted a proposal to amend Article 17 of the ICSP Statutes to include reference to generally recognized standards of ethical and professional conduct. E.R.B. Moore will forward the manuscript to all EB members.

International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes

The meeting was adjourned at 11.45 CEST.

Date / time of next meeting: to be determined. E.R.B. Moore will poll the EB members about a suitable date and time at the end of June or beginning of July for the next meeting.

Minutes prepared by A. Oren, 28th May 2026.

Action points

A. Oren, to forward the redacted minutes of the 30th April meeting of the Executive Board to all members of the ICSP, the Judicial Commission and the chairs of the Subcommittees on Taxonomy.

E.R.B. Moore, to post the redacted minutes of the 30th April meeting of the Executive Board on the ICSP website.

A. Oren, to send out the ballot to vote for officer positions for the EB-ICSP in the new term.

A. Oren, to send out the ballot to vote for election of three life members.

E.R.B. Moore and A. Oren, to submit the decision to award the C.B. van Niel International Prize to J. Chun, to be published in the *IJSEM*.

E.R.B. Moore, to notify the organizers of the IUMS conference in Lisbon in November of the organization and program of the 1-h ICSP sponsored session.

A. Oren, to coordinate the format and content of a BISMIS Live presentation on 18th July with E.R.B. Moore, A. Oren, M. Göker and M. del C. Montero-Calasanz.

EB members who are willing to share information on why they objected to the proposal to convert the Working Group on Education and Outreach to an Ad Hoc Subcommittee, to contact S.L.W. On no later than 26th June.

S.L.W. On, to forward any information received as above anonymously to M. del C. Montero-Calasanz and M. Göker.

E.R.B. Moore, to forward the proposal to amend Article 17 of the ICSP statutes submitted by J.A. Vázquez-Boland et al. to all EB members.

E.R.B. Moore, to poll the EB members about a suitable date and time for the next meeting.